

Chalcolithic Southern Levant

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As a prehistoric religion, the belief system of the Chalcolithic Southern Levant is predominantly reconstructed based on the material remnants of past ritual practices interpreted by archaeologists. The period experienced both continuity with Neolithic practices, as well as a suite of new ritual practices that reflect a transformation to the system of belief, which appears to have centered on the life cycle. Characteristic features of the period include diversity in burial practices, new architecture, a rise in the regional production of ritual objects connected with new forms of craft specialization, and the development of a shared visual language on such crafted ritual objects. New beliefs about bodily treatment and rites of passage are expressed in the diversity of mortuary practices, which include intramural primary burials, subterranean burials, and extramural secondary burials in decorated ossuaries in caves. Regarding architecture, certain buildings at sites like Teleilat Ghassul, En Gedi, and Gilat have sparked debates about the function of these buildings, as either temples or mortuary shrines while the appearance of both anthropomorphic and zoomorphic figurines raise questions about whether gods and goddesses were part of the ritual fabric of Chalcolithic society.

Date Range: 4500 BCE - 3600 BCE

Region: Levant

Region tags: Middle East, Israel

Levant

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gilead, Isaac. “Religio-Magic Behavior in the Chalcolithic Period of Palestine.” In Aharon Kempinski Memorial Volume: Studied in Archaeology and Related Disciplines, 103–28. Beersheva: Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, 2002. p.103-122
- Source 2: Rowan, Yorke M., and David Ilan. “The Meaning of Ritual Diversity in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant.” In *Cult in Context: Reconsidering Ritual in Archaeology*, 249–56. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2007.
- Source 3: Ilan, David, and Yorke M. Rowan. “Expediting Reincarnation in the Fifth Millennium BCE: Interpreting the Chalcolithic Ossuaries of the Southern Levant.” *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 38, no. 3 (January 1, 2019): 248–70. p.248-270

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– I don't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Field doesn't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The communities in this region do not yet have writing. It is unknown whether “oral scriptures” existed.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of this question is problematic as many sites are not fully excavated and thus it is hard to state percentages. However, En Gedi represents an important site whose function seems to have been primarily cultic as no domestic assemblage was recovered.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Formal ritual structures appear at En Gedi, Teleilat el-Ghassul, and Gilat, however the nature of these structures is debated (e.g., temple or mortuary shrine).

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces
- All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Depictions of zoomorphic beings appear on cultic objects, however it is unclear if these were interpreted during the Chalcolithic as supernatural

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of evidence is such that we cannot say with certainty what Chalcolithic communities believed. However, it has recently been proposed that ossuaries were connected to a belief in reincarnation. Ilan and Rowan (2019) argue that the materiality of clay ossuaries paired with the various forms these ossuaries take-anthro and zoomorphic-may reflect a belief system connected to reincarnation in this life. Ilan, David, and Y. M. Rowan. 2019. "Expediting Reincarnation in the Fifth Millennium BCE: Interpreting the Chalcolithic Ossuaries of the Southern Levant." *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 38 (3):248-270.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Secondary burial rites played a role for some communities wherein the body was defleshed and the bones interred in ceramic and stone ossuaries

↳ Cannibalism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: One of the characteristic features of this period is secondary burial in ceramic and stone ossuaries.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Possible mortuary centers for the preparation of the corpse at Gilat, Teleilat Ghassul, and En Gedi

Notes: Ilan, David, and Yorke M. Rowan. 2012. "Deconstructing and Recomposing the Narrative of Spiritual Life in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant (4500–3600 B.C.E)." *Archaeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association* 21 (1):89–113. Ilan, David, and Yorke M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171–194. Rowan, Yorke. M., and David Ilan. 2007. "The Meaning of Ritual Diversity in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant." In *Cult in Context: Reconsidering Ritual in Archaeology*, edited by David A. Barrowclough and Caroline Malone, 249–256. Oxford: Oxbow.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest sacrifice

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Gold rings were discovered in the Nahal Qanah cave, however this was an exceptional find. Copper objects including lost wax cast standards were discovered in other burial caves such as Peqi'in and Nahal Mishmar.

Notes: Bar-Adon, Pessah. 1980. *The Cave of the Treasure: The Finds from the Caves in Nahal Mishmar*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society. Gopher, Avi, and T. Tsuk. 1996. *The Nahal Qanah Cave: Earliest Gold in the Southern Levant*. Tel Aviv: Tel Aviv University. Shalem, Dina, Zvi Gal, and Howard Smithline. 2013. *Peqi'in: A Late Chalcolithic Burial Site Upper Galilee, Israel*. Tsemach, Israel: Kinneret Academic College/Ostracon.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Formal burial places appear during the Chalcolithic, however it is unclear whether the individuals were related by blood or social ties. Rowan, Y. M., and David Ilan. 2014. "The Subterranean Landscape of the Southern Levant during the Chalcolithic Period." In *Sacred Darkness: A Global Perspective on the Ritual Use of Caves*, edited by Holley Moyes, 87-107. University Press of Colorado. Shalem, Dina, Zvi Gal, and Howard Smithline. 2013. *Peqi'in: A Late Chalcolithic Burial Site Upper Galilee, Israel*. Tsemach, Israel: Kinneret Academic College/Ostracon.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Dolmen fields

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the emphasis on fertility and regeneration, this seems highly unlikely. However, there simply is not data available to say whether celibacy was a requirement, perhaps for a subset of the population.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No data available to answer this question

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this was a required practice

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There remains disagreement with regard to how best to classify the political organization of Chalcolithic society.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Research proposed by Amzallag (2018) has argued that certain copper pieces in the Nahal Mishmar hoard—long believed to be a product of Chalcolithic communities—encoded secret copper-related production knowledge in the form of a visual code, as a type of proto writing system. According to this theory, icons and symbols cast into certain objects were used in a logographic way to encode knowledge of the smelting process. This theory has been met with critique, however (see Wilson-Wright 2020). Amzallag, Nissim. 2018. "Visual Code in the Nahal Mishmar Hoard: The Earliest Case of Proto-Writing?" *Antiguo Oriente* 16:45-91. Wilson-Wright, Aren M. 2020. "The Lost Language of the Ghassulians: Proto-Writing at Nahal Mishmar?: A Response to "When did people start writing in the Levant?" By Nissim Amzallag." *Bible and Interpretation*. <https://bibleinterp.arizona.edu/articles/lost-language-ghassulians-proto-writing-nahal-mishmar>

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Chalcolithic Southern Levant, Ilan, David, and Yorke M. Rowan. "Expediting Reincarnation in the Fifth Millennium BCE: Interpreting the Chalcolithic Ossuaries of the Southern Levant". *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 38, no. 3 (January 1, 2019): 248-70. p.248-270

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Reference: Chalcolithic Southern Levant, Arama, Milena Gošić. "Temples in the Ghassulian Culture: Terminology and Social Implications". *Етноантрополошки Проблеми, Н. С. Год. 11, no. 3 (January 1, 2016): 869-93. p.869-893*